

Assessment of CSF ADA and CRP Levels in Differential Diagnosis of Meningitis in AdultsC. Komal¹, V. Praveen², K.Vani³¹Associate Professor of General Medicine, Osmania Medical College / General Hospital, Hyderabad²Associate Professor of General Medicine, Osmania Medical College / General Hospital, Hyderabad³Assistant Professor of Biochemistry, Govt. Medical College, Nagarkurnool

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Infections involving the CNS, particularly meningitis and encephalitis are likely to arouse tremendous anxiety in both the physician and patients. Reliable, cost effective, rapid diagnostic tests which can be performed in any standard pathology laboratory could be of help in the differentiation of various types of meningitis in adults. In this regard, C - reactive protein level and Adenosine deaminase activity can be used as rapid tests in the differential diagnosis of meningitis. ADA estimation is useful in diagnosis of tuberculous meningitis. CRP estimation has been documented to be helpful in diagnosing pyogenic meningitis. The levels of both ADA and CRP are low in cases of viral meningitis.

Aim of the Study: Assessment of cerebrospinal fluid Adenosine deaminase and C Reactive protein in the differential diagnosis of meningitis in adults.

Methods: CSF samples were obtained from 50 patients who presented to the casualty and Outpatient department of Osmania General Hospital. Diagnosis of meningitis was based on the clinical presentation and CSF analysis.

Results: In our study, out of a total of 50 patients, 25 patients were diagnosed as tubercular meningitis based on the clinical features and CSF analysis. The mean ADA activity was 14.36 in the Tuberculous meningitis group, the result being statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The sensitivity and specificity were 72% and 100% respectively when a cut-off value of ADA of 10U/l was used. CSF-CRP is significantly higher in pyogenic meningitis compared to non-pyogenic meningitis. The sensitivity and specificity of the test was 90% and 100% respectively with an accuracy of 98%.

Conclusion: 2 rapid diagnostic tests-CRP and ADA activity in the CSF can help in the differential diagnosis of pyogenic from non-pyogenic and tubercular from viral meningitis respectively. CRP being elevated in pyogenic meningitis and ADA activity noted to be higher in tuberculous meningitis. The levels of ADA and CRP are low in viral meningitis. However, these tests should be interpreted judiciously in the light of the patients' clinical manifestations and the results of CSF analysis.

Keywords: CSF; CRP; ADA; Pyogenic meningitis; non-pyogenic meningitis; Tubercular meningitis.

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Introduction

Infectious diseases remain a major cause of death and disability for millions of people around the world, despite decades of dramatic progress in their treatment and prevention. Each infectious agent can cause a spectrum of illnesses, which challenges the physician's diagnostic skills. The central nervous system (CNS) may appear protected from perturbations in the environment by a blood brain barrier - a system of tight junction around capillaries that resist the entry of pathogens, inflammatory cells and macromolecules into the subarachnoid space and the brain. However, the barrier fails to resist the intensity of the microbial world, and its presence also cause difficulty in the

delivery of antimicrobial agents in adequate concentrations. As vital tissues are involved, CNS infection can cause devastating sequelae and in some cases may result in both neurological and medical emergencies. [1]

Aim of the Study

1. To estimate the C reactive protein and Adenosine deaminase levels in CSF of patients with meningitis.
2. To evaluate whether C-reactive protein and Adenosine deaminase levels could be used to differentiate the various types of meningitis in adults.

Material and Methods: CSF samples were obtained from 50 patients who presented to the casualty and Outpatient Department of Osmania General Hospital, Hyderabad during the period of September 2020 to July 2022.

Collection of data

- Criteria for diagnosis of meningitis
- Triad of fever, headache, nuchal rigidity.
- Altered mental status.
- Nausea, vomiting and photophobia.
- Seizures.
- Signs of meningeal irritation.
- 50 patients were included in the study

Inclusion criteria

- Age > 18 years.
- Clinical features suggestive of meningitis

Exclusion criteria

- Age < 18 years.
- A patient with acute infections at sites other than central nervous system.
- Patients in whom lumbar puncture is contraindicated.
- Associated severe hepatic dysfunction.
- Females on oral contraceptives and intrauterine device
- Severe dyslipidemia.
- Patients on steroids

Results:

Table 1: Age Distribution of Meningitis

Gender	Total Cases	TBM	Fungal Meningitis	Pyogenic	Viral
Male	39	21	0	6	12
Female	11	4	0	3	4
Total	50	25	0	9	16

Table 2: Percentage of Male and Females in Different Meningitis

Types of Meningitis	No of Cases	Percentage
TBM	25	50
Fungal Meningitis	0	0
Pyogenic Meningitis	9	18
Viral Meningitis	16	32
Total	50	100

Figure 1: Clinical Presentation of Meningitis

Figure 2: Neutrophil Count

Figure 3: CRP levels are elevated in pyogenic meningitis

Table 3: ADA in Different Meningitis

Type of Meningitis	Number	ADA Levels
Tubercular	25	14.36
Pyogenic	9	4.77
Viral	16	1.018
Total	50	

Table 4: CRP in different meningitis

Type of Meningitis	Number	P value of CRP
Tubercular	25	
Pyogenic	9	<0.001
Viral	16	
Fungal		

* P Value of CRP is Significant in Pyogenic Meningitis

Figure 4: Sensitivity and Specificity of CRP

Table 5: Sensitivity and Specificity of tubercular meningitis

Type of Meningitis	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
Tubercular	72%	100%	100%	78.125%	86%
Pyogenic	11.1%	47%	5.263%	66.6%	34%
Viral					
Fungal					

Sensitivity and Specificity of tubercular meningitis are 72% and 100% respectively. P value is <0.001 which is very significant

Figure 5: Outcome

Discussion

Infections involving the CNS, particularly meningitis and encephalitis are likely to arouse tremendous anxiety in both the patients and physician. Perhaps this to be expected considering the high mortality rates associated with these infections and the neurologic sequelae that may

linger in those who recover. CSF ADA activities are raised in tuberculous meningitis and their use has been suggested to help differentiate tuberculous meningitis from viral and bacterial meningitis. [2]

Sang-Ho Choi et al studied ADA activity in CSF of 182 patients with meningitis. The mean ADA level in the tuberculous meningitis group was 12.7±7.5

U/l and it was significantly higher than the other groups (3.10 ± 2.9 U/l; $p < 0.001$). The sensitivity and specificity was 0.83 and 0.95 respectively when a cut-off value of 7U/l was used. [3] Pettersson et al reports sensitivity of 1.0 and specificity of 0.99 when a cut-off value of 20 U/l was used, but in that study there were only 3 enrolled tuberculous meningitis patients. [4]

Chotmongkol V et al [5] identified a CSF ADA level of 15.5U/l as the best cut-off value to differentiate tuberculous meningitis and non-tuberculous meningitis, with a sensitivity of 75% and specificity of 93%. When tuberculous meningitis was compared with aseptic and carcinomatous meningitis, a CSF ADA level of 19.0 U/l was the best cut-off value for differentiation, with a sensitivity of 69% and a specificity of 94%. [5]

In our study, a total of 25 patients were diagnosed as tubercular meningitis based on the clinical features and CSF analysis. The mean ADA activity was 14.36 U/l in the tuberculous meningitis group; 4.77 in the pyogenic meningitis group; 1.018 in the viral meningitis group. Comparing the ADA activity in the 3 groups, the difference was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) in the tuberculous meningitis group compared to the other groups. The sensitivity and specificity was 72% and 100% respectively when a cut-off value of ADA of 10U/l was used.

Malan C et al [6] showed that in both bacterial and TBM groups, the mean ADA level in the CSF was significantly higher than in aseptic meningitis ($p < 0.001$), but a significant difference was not shown between bacterial meningitis and TBM groups. Similar results were noted in our study where the mean ADA value in viral meningitis was 1.018 which was well below the cut-off value.

However, the value of ADA in the differential diagnosis of bacterial meningitis and fungal meningitis is controversial and there has been no cut-off value of CSF ADA activity.

In our study, we found that the value of CSF ADA was 4.77 in pyogenic meningitis. Some studies have reported a lower efficacy of this test and show an overlap between tuberculous meningitis and bacterial meningitis, so we used the higher cut-off

value of 10 U/l in order to increase the sensitivity of ADA and overcome this lacuna. Martinez et al [7] reported that CSF ADA activities were not significantly different between the group with tuberculous meningitis and the group with cryptococcal meningitis in AIDS patients. According to a study by Lopez, CSF ADA levels were raised in cases of neurobrucellosis and cryptococcal meningitis. It has been postulated that the selective increase of ADA depends on the degree of stimulation of T lymphocytes rather than the total numbers. Ena et al reported CSF ADA elevation in tuberculous meningitis patients with significant T cell depleted AIDS.

Gambhir IS et al found that the mean CSF ADA levels in TBM patients was 9.61 ± 4.10 U/l and was significantly elevated as compared to viral encephalitis and enteric encephalopathy cases; but the difference was insignificant in comparison to pyogenic meningitis and cerebral malaria. ADA exists as 2 isoenzymes, ADA (1) and ADA (2). It appears that ADA (2) isoenzyme originates mainly from monocytes and macrophages. ADA isoenzyme analysis by Schutte CM et al. concluded that the ratio of ADA (2) / ADA (Total) was > 0.8 in patients with tuberculous meningitis. The level of ADA (2) was tested in our study.

It has been suggested by Piras and Gakis that ADA levels in CSF may help differentiate TBM from viral meningitis and further that TBM and bacterial meningitis 'differ clearly from one another as regards the relationship of ADA to the number of cells. [9]

As in previous studies, it is apparent from the results of our study that the level of ADA in CSF was considerably elevated in tuberculous meningitis compared with viral meningitis. This conclusion has proved to be extremely beneficial in the treatment of viral meningitis where patients have been started inadvertently on prolonged courses of anti-tubercular medication with the misdiagnosis of tubercular meningitis. We found that the ADA levels correlated with the severity of clinical presentation. Patients who presented with altered sensorium, cranial nerve involvement and hemiparesis were noted to have higher ADA values. However, there was no clear correlation with the outcome.

Table 6: Showing the various studies on ADA with the cut-off values used and sensitivity and specificity obtained

Study	Number of patients diagnosed with TBM	ADA cutoff level	Sensitivity	Specificity
Rajendra Prasad et al [10]	29	3.3	100%	97.87%
Kashyap et al [11]	117	11.39	82%	83%
Gautum N et al [12]	20	6.97	85%	88%
Pettersson et al [2]	3	20	100%	99%
Chotmongkol et al [5]	16	15.5	75%	93%

Choi et al [13]	36	7	83%	95%
Ribera et al [7]	32		100%	99%
Lopez et al [4]		10	48%	100%
Rohani MY et al [14]	14	9		87.69%
Present study	25	10	72%	100%

Previous studies conducted by Goran Rajs et al, have observed that CSF-CRP levels are higher in gram-negative pyogenic meningitis compared to gram positive pyogenic meningitis suggesting that infection with gram-negative bacteria probably enhances permeability of CRP through the blood brain barrier.

In a study conducted by Vaishnavi C et al, CRP in CSF was significantly higher in patients with pyogenic meningitis compared to tubercular meningitis. Authors concluded that the estimation of CRP in the differential diagnosis of meningitis might be made to give a preliminary diagnosis of meningitis. [15]

Riberio MH et al estimated the levels of CRP in CSF from 33 patients with bacterial meningitis, 21 patients with lymphocytic meningitis and 54 controls. 100% of these patients with bacterial meningitis were correctly classified on the basis of measurement of CRP levels in CSF. No more than 4% of patients were incorrectly classified as belonging to the bacterial group on the basis of CRP levels in CSF. In conclusion authors recommend the estimation of CRP in CSF in the differentiation of bacterial from non-bacterial meningitis [16].

Hemavani V et al evaluated the role of CRP in CSF in differentiation of meningitis. The study included 499 CSF samples from cases of viral, pyogenic, tuberculous and fungal meningitis and 580 normal CSF samples. CRP positive by qualitative latex agglutination test was seen in 73.3% of CSF samples from partially treated pyogenic meningitis and 92% among pyogenic meningitis cases.

All suspected cases of tuberculosis meningitis were negative for CRP in the CSF while only 1 out of CSF samples for bacteriologically confirmed tuberculous meningitis was positive. CRP was raised in 27.2% and 12.5% of CSF samples from candidal and cryptococcal meningitis cases respectively while none of the 102 samples from suspected viral meningitis and 580 non-meningitis cases was positive for CRP in the CSF. The study concludes that CSF CRP determination can be of value to differentiate pyogenic versus other microbial meningitis etiology. However, it cannot differentiate between tuberculosis, fungal and viral meningitis. [17]

In our study, the CRP in CSF of patients with pyogenic meningitis, tubercular meningitis and viral meningitis were; 31.44mg/dl, 0.86mg/dl and

1.01mg/dl respectively. Tankhiwale SS et al investigated 75 clinically, biochemically and microscopically diagnosed cases of pyogenic meningitis including 28 adults and 47 pediatric patients. 31 out of 75 cases (42.66%) were positive for CSF-CRP while 34 were positive for only serum CRP. Thus, total of 66 patients showed raised CRP levels in either in serum or CSF while only 27 yielded bacterial growth in culture. The difference was statistically significant. Hence, the authors concluded that estimation of CRP in CSF and serum help as an early marker for rapid diagnosis of pyogenic meningitis. Patients with hepatic dysfunction, dyslipidemia, females on oral contraceptives, patients on steroids were not included in the study as each of these factors independently affect CRP levels.

We suggest a protocol for the early differential diagnosis of meningitis using CSF ADA activity and CRP levels. In case of a patient with unexplained fever, headache, nausea/vomiting, a spinal tap with blood cultures is indicated. Before a spinal tap, a brain computed tomography (CT) may be needed in case of altered mental status or papilledema, or of focal neurologic deficits. If CSF analysis shows polymorphonuclear leukocyte dominant pleocytosis (CSF WBC>1500/mm³), it is almost always pyogenic meningitis.

CRP can be used as a rapid confirmatory test since elevated CRP levels are highly suggestive of pyogenic meningitis. Send the gram stain and CSF culture and start antibiotics for pyogenic meningitis. If CSF analysis shows pleocytosis<1500/mm³, with or without polymorphonuclear leukocyte dominant, since tuberculous meningitis may first be manifested as a polymorphonuclear leukocyte dominant pattern, check the CSF AFB smear/culture, fungus smear/culture, Cryptococcus latex agglutination test, viral PCR and CSF ADA. In cases with a lymphocyte dominant pattern CSF ADA can be used to determine the possibility of tuberculous meningitis versus viral meningitis. Early confirmatory diagnosis and aggressive management can help prevent serious CNS complications. 2 rapid diagnostic tests-CRP and ADA activity in the CSF can help in the differential diagnosis of pyogenic from non-pyogenic and tubercular from viral meningitis respectively.

CRP being elevated in pyogenic meningitis and ADA activity noted to be higher in tuberculous meningitis. The levels of ADA and CRP are low in viral meningitis. However, these tests should be

interpreted judiciously in the light of the patients' clinical manifestations and the CSF characteristics.

Conclusion

- Most common meningitis is present study is Tubercular meningitis, followed by Viral Meningitis.
- Tubercular meningitis is seen mostly in younger Age group, whereas pyogenic meningitis in extremes of age group.
- Males are affected than females in are 3 types of Meningitis in present study.
- Fever & headache was present in all cases of Meningitis (100%). 70% presented with altered sensorium.
- Average cell count is more in pyogenic meningitis least in viral meningitis
- Tubercular & Pyogenic meningitis had raised protein levels and decreased sugar levels.
- CSF ADA activity was higher in patients with tubercular meningitis when compared to pyogenic and viral meningitis.
- CSF –CRP levels were higher in pyogenic meningitis than in non-pyogenic meningitis.
- ADA levels correlated with clinical presentation but not with the outcome of tubercular meningitis.
- All deaths occurred in Tubercular meningitis group.

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